

FINAL REPORT

Test Facility Study No. 20458624
Sponsor Reference No. BDT272-23-013

**Single Dose Pharmacokinetics of BDT272 after Oral and Intravenous
Administration in Female Göttingen Minipigs**

Non-GLP

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1. SUMMARY

The objective of this study was to investigate the pharmacokinetics of BDT272, when given orally by gavage and intravenously to female Gottingen minipigs. In addition, the possible oral bioavailability of BDT272 was assessed.

The study was conducted on the following dates according to the Study Plan and the last Study Plan Amendment ([Appendix 1](#)).

Initiation of Dosing: 15 Aug 2023

Administration of the Test Material:

- Period 1 15 Aug 2023
- Period 2 22 Aug 2023

Completion of In-life Phase: 23 Aug 2023

The study design was as follows:

Text Table 1
Experimental Design

Period ^b	Test Material Id.	Dose Level (mg/kg)	Dose Volume ^a (mL/kg)	Dose Concentration (mg/mL)	Dose Route	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
						Females	Females
1	BDT272	0.5	0.5	1	IV	4	1-4
2		2	1	2	PO		

Id.= identification.

^a Based on the most recent body weight measurement.

^b There was a wash-out period of one week between the consecutive periods

2. RESULTS

Results	
Mortality	No mortality occurred.
Clinical Observations	No clinical signs were noted.
Body Weights (Appendix 4)	Body weight ranged between 17.6 and 20.3 kg on the day of intravenous administration (Period 1, Day 1). Only normal fluctuations in body weight were observed during the study period.
Bioanalysis	Plasma samples were analyzed for BDT272 total concentrations using a validated analytical method with a lower limit of quantitation (LLOQ) of 20 ng/mL. At the request of the Sponsor, values below the LLOQ were extrapolated and the extrapolated values were used for the pharmacokinetic evaluation, see deviation in Text Table 4.

Results	
Pharmacokinetics (Appendix 5)	<p>BDT272 was quantifiable in female Göttingen minipigs up to 2 hours after IV administration. Following PO administration, BDT272 was quantifiable in plasma up to 3, 6, 4 or 4 hours (Animal No. 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively). In both periods, reliable extrapolated values below the limit of quantification were present throughout the 24 hours sampling period. The plasma concentrations of BDT272 increased moderately fast, as median t_{max} values for BDT272 were observed at 3 hours postdose following PO administration and individual t_{max} values ranged from 2 to 3 hours. Following IV administration, C_0 could not be back extrapolated in Animal No. 1 and was therefore excluded from descriptive statistics.</p> <p>BDT272 was moderately cleared and highly distributed. Individual $t_{1/2}$ ranged from 3.81 to 5.88 hours after IV dosing and from 7.90 to 13.1 hours after PO dosing.</p> <p>Average absolute oral bioavailability of BDT272 in female Göttingen minipig plasma was low since F was 34.5% based on AUC_{0-inf} and 29.0% based on AUC_{last}.</p>

3. CONCLUSION

Göttingen minipigs were treated with BDT272 via a single intravenous administration at a dose level of 0.5 mg/kg (Period 1) followed by a single oral administration at 2 mg/kg (Period 2).

The administration of BDT272 was well tolerated. No mortality was observed, and no clinical signs were noted during the study.

BDT272 was quantifiable in female Göttingen minipigs throughout the 24 hours sampling period following both IV and PO administration. The plasma concentrations of BDT272 increased moderately fast, as median t_{max} values for BDT272 were observed at 3 hours postdose following PO administration.

BDT272 was moderately cleared and highly distributed. Individual $t_{1/2}$ ranged from 3.81 to 5.88 hours after IV dosing and from 7.90 to 13.1 hours after PO dosing. Average absolute oral bioavailability of BDT272 in female Göttingen minipig plasma was low since F was 34.5% based on AUC_{0-inf} and 29.0% based on AUC_{tlast} .

4. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was conducted in accordance with the Study Plan and the last Study Plan Amendment presented in [Appendix 1](#) with the following requirements and exceptions.

Text Table 2
Additional Study Plan Deliverables

Age at Initiation of Dosing	11 to 12 months old
Body Weight Range at Initiation of Dosing	17.6 – 20.3 kg
Environmental Conditions	The actual daily mean temperature during the study period was 19°C with an actual daily mean relative humidity of 84 to 92%. The values that were outside the targeted range occurred with a maximum of 92% and were without a noticeable effect on the clinical condition of the animals or on the outcome of the study.
Food	Approximately 320 g of food was offered in two daily portions at the beginning and end of the working day.
Duration of Intravenous Dose Administration in Period 1	The duration of intravenous dose administration in Period 1 was 94, 27, 24, and 23 seconds for Animal Nos. 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

In addition to the deviations that are required to be reported, the Study Director deemed to include in the report the following events that are relevant to the reproducibility of the study.

Text Table 3
Study Events

Event
The intravenous dose administration of Animal No. 1 was paused for 23 seconds. As a result, the total time from start of dosing until completion of dosing for this animal (94 seconds) was longer compared to the other animals.
Veterinary care was available throughout the course of the study, and animals were examined by the veterinary staff as warranted by clinical signs or other changes. All veterinary examinations and recommended therapeutic treatments were documented in the study records.

All deviations that occurred during the study have been authorized/acknowledged by the Study Director, assessed for impact, and documented in the study records. All Study Plan deviations and those SOP deviations that could have impacted the quality or integrity of the study are listed below.

None of the deviations were considered to have impacted the overall integrity of the study or the interpretation of the study results and conclusions.

Text Table 4
Deviations

Study Plan Section No.	Deviation	Impact
10	On the day of release, animals were not observed for clinical observations.	No clinical observations were noted during the study or during the preliminary check on the morning of release. Thus, it can be assumed that no clinical signs were observed on the day of release. No impact on the study integrity.
11.2	In Period 1, the centrifugation of the 0.083h postdose blood sample from Animal No. 1 was started 37 minutes after sample collection.	Samples were stored on ice until centrifugation. Therefore, this minimal delay in centrifugation is not expected to affect the sample integrity.

11.4	Concentrations below the lower limit of quantification (BLQ values) were extrapolated during bioanalysis and these extrapolated values were used in PK evaluation, instead of setting these values to zero.	Since extrapolated values were considered sufficiently reliable, the impact on the study integrity is considered minimal.
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5. RETENTION OF RECORDS AND SAMPLES

All study-specific raw data, documentation, protocol, and final reports from this study were archived at the Testing Facility by no later than the date of final report issue. All materials generated by Charles River from this study were transferred to a Charles River archive. Two years after issue of the final report, the Sponsor will be contacted to determine the disposition of materials associated with the study.

Electronic data generated by the Test Facility and Bioanalytical Test Site were archived as noted above, except that data collected using Provantis and Dispense, files stored on M-Files (Study Plan (amendments) and reporting files) and study deviations were archived at the Charles River Laboratories facility location in Wilmington, Massachusetts, USA.

Disposition of residual/retained analytical samples was as described in the table below.

Text Table 5
Disposition of Residual/Retained Samples

Sample Type	Disposition
Reserve Samples (Plasma, Aliquot B)	Discarded
Bioanalytical (CR-STN)	Discarded

6. REPORT APPROVAL

All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.

Appendix 1

STUDY PLAN AMENDMENT NO. 02

Test Facility Study No. 20458624

Sponsor Reference No. BDT272-23-013

**Single Dose Pharmacokinetics of BDT272 after Oral and Intravenous
Administration in Female Göttingen Minipigs**

Non-GLP

SPONSOR:

Biodol Therapeutics
CAP Alpha
Avenue de l'Europe
34830 Clapiers
France

TEST FACILITY:

Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V.
Hambakenwetering 7
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The Netherlands

Appendix 1**SUMMARY OF CHANGES AND JUSTIFICATIONS****Study Plan effective date: 09 Aug 2023**

Note: When applicable, additions are indicated in bold underlined text and deletions are indicated in bold strikethrough text in the affected sections of the document.

Item or Section(s)	Justification
Amendment No. 01	Effective Date: 14 Aug 2023
4. RESPONSIBLE PERSONNEL	Change in Study Director due to temporary leave of the original Study Director.
Amendment No. 02	Effective Date: See date of Study Director approval
4. RESPONSIBLE PERSONNEL	The responsibilities will be re-assigned to the original Study Director.

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Appendix 1**1. OBJECTIVE(S)**

The objective of this study is to investigate the pharmacokinetics of BDT272, when given orally by gavage and intravenously to female Gottingen minipigs. In addition, the possible oral bioavailability of BDT272 will be assessed.

2. PROPOSED STUDY SCHEDULE

Proposed study dates are listed below. Actual dates will be included in the Final Report.

Experimental Starting Date: 14 Aug 2023
(First date of study-specific data collection; allocation)

Experimental Completion Date: 09 Nov 2023
(Last date on which data are collected)

Initiation of Dosing: 15 Aug 2023

Completion of In-life: 23 Aug 2023
(Release of animals from study)

Administration of Test Material:

- Period 1: 15 Aug 2023

- Period 2: 22 Aug 2023

Blood Sampling for
Pharmacokinetics:

- Period 1: 15-16 Aug 2023

- Period 2: 22-23 Aug 2023

Draft Report: 10 Nov 2023

Final Report: Within 6 months after issuing the draft report (i.e. latest
10 May 2024)

The contributions from Principal Investigators to Study Director are proposed at the dates indicated below to allow inclusion in Draft Report.

Bioanalytical QC'd Results Available: 06 Oct 2023 (QC'd data required at this date to allow
Pharmacokinetic analysis)

Pharmacokinetic Draft Report: 27 Oct 2023

3. SPONSOR

Role	Name	Contact Information
Sponsor Representative/ Study Monitor	Pierre Sokoloff	Address as cited for Sponsor Tel: +33 7 70 41 63 68 E-mail: pierre.sokoloff@biodol.eu

Appendix 1**4. RESPONSIBLE PERSONNEL**

Role/Phase	Name	Contact Information
Study Director from 09 Aug 2023 to 13 Aug 2023 and from 07 Sep 2023 onwards	Freeke van Pijpen, MSc	Address as cited for Test Facility Tel: +31 73 640 6700 E-mail: freeke.vanpijpen@crl.com
Study Director from 14 Aug 2023 onwards to 06 Sep 2023	Moniek van 't Root, MSc	Address as cited for Test Facility Tel: +31 73 640 6700 E-mail: moniek.vantroot@crl.com
Test Facility Management	Harry Emmen, MSc	Address as cited for Test Facility Tel: +31 73 640 6700 E-mail: harry.emmen@crl.com
Individual Scientist (IS)		
PK evaluation	Name will be included in the Final Report.	
Principal Investigator (PI)		
Bioanalysis	Camille Tanguy, MSc (PI)	Charles River Laboratories Saint-Nazaire 1 rue Graham Bell ZI de Brais – CS 40309 44605 Saint-Nazaire Cedex France Tel : +33 2 28 54 31 29 E-mail: camille.tanguy@crl.com
	Solenn Vincent, MSc (Deputy PI)	Address as cited for Bioanalysis Test Site Tel : +33 2 51 10 10 93 E-mail: solenn.vincent@crl.com

Each IS and PI is required to report all deviations or other circumstances that could affect the quality or integrity of the study to the Study Director in a timely manner for authorization/acknowledgement. The PI of Bioanalysis will provide an Excel and the IS of the Pharmacokinetic Evaluation will provide a report addressing their assigned phase of the study, which will be included as an appendix to the Final Report.

The IS Phase Report will include the following:

- A listing of critical computerized systems used in the conduct and/or interpretation of the assigned study phase

5. TEST MATERIALS**5.1. Test Material Characterization**

A Certificate of Analysis or equivalent documentation will be provided for inclusion in the Final Report (if available).

5.2. Test Material Identification**5.2.1. Test Material**

Identification: BDT272
Batch (Lot) Number: L22024-A

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Expiry Date:	07 October 2023 (retest date)
Physical Description:	Off-white powder
Purity/Composition:	100% UPLC
Storage Conditions:	Room temperature set to maintain 21°C protected from light desiccated

Additional information

Test Facility Test Material Number:	213138/F
Purity/Composition Correction Factor:	No correction factor required
Test Material Handling:	Use amber glassware or wrap container in aluminum foil
Stability in vehicle:	
50% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS + 0.5% Tween 80	Stability for at least 24 hours at room temperature under normal laboratory light conditions and 8 days in the refrigerator is confirmed over the concentration range 1 to 50 mg/mL (solutions, 500 mL bulk volume), Test Facility Study No. 20397039

5.2.2. Vehicle – Period 1 (IV)

Identification: 15% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS

5.2.3. Vehicle – Period 2 (PO)

Identification: 50% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS + 0.5% Tween-80

5.3. Reserve Samples

For each batch (lot) of test material and if practically possible, a reserve sample will be collected and maintained under the appropriate storage conditions by the Test Facility.

5.4. Test Material Inventory and Disposition

Records of the receipt, distribution, storage, and disposition of test materials will be maintained.

5.5. Safety

The following safety instruction(s) apply to this study:

- Standard safety precautions specified in Charles River Den Bosch procedures
- Specific safety precautions are provided in the Charles River Den Bosch internal EH&S test material risk assessment

Appendix 1**6. DOSE FORMULATION AND ANALYSIS****6.1. Preparation of Formulations**

Preparation Details

Dose Formulation	Administration Dose Form	Procedure	Frequency of Preparation	Storage Conditions Set to Maintain
Period 1 (IV)	Solution	The test material is weighed and finely grinded using a mortar and pestle. Vehicle is then added in small portions with continuous grinding (using mortar and pestle) until a fine homogenous paste is created. Subsequently, the rest of the vehicle is added. The formulation is then homogenized to visually acceptable levels.	On the day before dose administration.	4°C, protected from light
Period 2 (PO)	Solution/Suspension	The formulation for IV administration will be filtered using a 0.2 µM filter prior to dose administration.	On the day before dose administration.	4°C, protected from light

Adjustments will be made for specific gravity of the vehicle. No correction will be made for the purity/composition of the test material.

Any residual volumes from each dosing occasion will be discarded unless otherwise requested by the Study Director.

6.2. Sample Collection and Analysis

Analysis of test material in vehicle for concentration, stability, homogeneity will not be performed, however, to limit the impact, the test material preparation will be performed with approved procedures and documented in detail. Formulations will be visually inspected for homogeneity prior to use and all formulations will be used within 6 hours after removal from the refrigerator.

7. TEST SYSTEM

Species: Minipig
 Strain: Göttingen
 Animal Condition: Outbred, microbiologically defined, non-naïve
 Animal Supplier: Ellegaard Göttingen minipigs, Sorø Landevej 302, DK-4261 Dalmose, Denmark
 Treatment History: The non-naïve animals were last used in the following studies: Test Facility Study No. 20420875, 20420876, or 20432938. Animals were not used after 16 May 2023. Based on the half-lives of the test

Appendix 1

materials dosed in previous studies, the wash-out period is considered to be sufficient.

Number of Females: 4
Target Age at the
Initiation of Dosing: 10 to 11 months
Target Weight at the
Initiation of Dosing: 15 to 18 kg

The actual age and weight of the animals at the initiation of dosing will be listed in the Final Report.

7.1. Animal Identification

Method: Each animal will be identified using an ear tag and/or subcutaneously implanted electronic identification chip.

7.2. Environmental Acclimation

The animals selected for this study originate from the animal pool housed at the Test Facility, therefore these animals are already acclimated to the Test Facility toxicology accommodation and are directly available for the commencement of dosing.

7.3. Selection, Assignment, and Disposition of Animals

Selection: The females selected for the study will be assigned to Group 1.
Disposition: The disposition of all animals will be documented in the study records.

8. HUSBANDRY**8.1. Housing**

Housing: Group housed (up to 4 animals).
These housing conditions will be maintained unless deemed inappropriate by the Study Director and/or Clinical Veterinarian. The room(s) in which the animals will be kept will be documented in the study records.
Animals will be socially housed with the exception of times when they are separated for designated study procedures/activities.

Caging: Stainless steel cages and sterilized sawdust will be used as bedding material.

Cage Identification: Color-coded cage card indicating Test Facility Study No., group, animal/tattoo number(s).

Appendix 1**8.2. Animal Enrichment**

For psychological/environmental enrichment, animals will be provided with items such as a rug and balls, except when interrupted by study procedures/activities.

8.3. Environmental Conditions

The targeted conditions for animal room environment will be as follows:

Temperature:	15 to 21°C
Humidity:	30 to 70%
Light Cycle:	12-hours light and 12-hours dark (except during designated procedures) (nightlight during the night period)
Ventilation:	Ten or more air changes per hour

8.4. Food

Diet:	KLIBA 3000PSS15 (Kaiseraugst, Switzerland)
Type:	Kibble (alternate diet may be provided on individual animal basis as warranted as approved by the Study Director).
Frequency/Ration:	An appropriate ration of feed (based on body weights, details will be recorded in the raw data) will be offered divided over two daily portions at the beginning and end of the working day.

During the night prior to the days of dosing, animals will be fasted, but water will be available. On the days of dosing, the first daily food ration will be available approximately 2 hour after dosing.

In addition, minipigs may be rewarded with apple juice, marshmallows or raisins during training and handling, when necessary.

Analysis:	Results of analysis for nutritional components and environmental contaminants are provided by the supplier and are on file at the Test Facility. It is considered that there are no known contaminants in the feed that would interfere with the objectives of the study.
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8.5. Water

Type:	Municipal tap water.
Frequency/Ration:	Freely available to each animal via an automatic watering system (except during designated procedures).
Analysis:	Periodic analysis of the water is performed, and results of these analyses are on file at the Test Facility. It is considered that there are no known contaminants in the water that could interfere with the outcome of the study.

Appendix 1**8.6. Veterinary Care**

Veterinary care will be available throughout the course of the study and animals will be examined by the veterinary staff as warranted by clinical signs or other changes. In the event that animals show signs of illness or distress, the responsible veterinarian may make initial recommendations about treatment of the animal(s) and/or alteration of study procedures, which must be approved by the Study Director. Treatment of the animal(s) for minor injuries or ailments may be approved without prior consultation with the Sponsor representative when such treatment does not impact fulfillment of the study objectives. If the condition of the animal(s) warrants significant therapeutic intervention or alterations in study procedures, the Sponsor representative will be contacted, when possible, to discuss appropriate action. If the condition of the animal(s) is such that emergency measures must be taken, the Study Director and/or attending veterinarian will attempt to consult with the Sponsor representative prior to responding to the medical crisis, but the Study Director and/or veterinarian has authority to act immediately at his/her discretion to alleviate suffering. The Sponsor representative will be fully informed of any such events.

9. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Period ^b	Test Material Id.	Dose Level (mg/kg)	Dose Volume ^a (mL/kg)	Dose Concentration (mg/mL)	Dose Route	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
						Females	Females
1	BDT272	0.5	0.5	1	IV	4	1-4
2		2	1	2	PO		

Id.= identification.

^a Based on the most recent body weight measurement.

^b There will be a wash-out period of one week between the consecutive periods

9.1. Administration of Test Materials**9.1.1. Period 1 – IV Bolus**

Dose Route: Intravenous (slow bolus) injection into the ear vein

Treatment: Once

Frequency:

Treatment Duration: Single dose

Method: The day of dosing will be designated as Day 1. The dose formulations will be stirred continuously during dosing. The dose volume for each animal will be based on the most recent body weight measurement. The animals will be temporarily placed in a sling-type restraining device during injection. The dose will be given using a flexible catheter with butterfly needle connected to a disposable syringe. The dose will be administered as quickly as practically possible and the exact dosing time in seconds will be recorded. The time of ending the intravenous bolus injection will be designated as time 0.

Dose pot identification via Provantis will be used as additional check to verify the dosing procedure according to Standard Operating Procedures.

Appendix 1**9.1.2. Period 2 – Oral Gavage**

Dose Route: Oral gavage

Treatment: Once

Frequency:

Treatment Duration: Single dose

Method: The dose formulations will be stirred continuously during dosing. The animals will be temporarily placed in a v-trog restraining device during dosing. The doses will be given using a flexible catheter. Each dose will be followed by a tap water flush of approximately 20 mL.

Dose pot identification via Provantis will be used as additional check to verify the dosing procedure according to Standard Operating Procedures.

10. IN-LIFE PROCEDURES, OBSERVATIONS, AND MEASUREMENTS

General In-life Assessments –Study Animals

Parameter	Population(s)	Frequency (minimum required)	Comments
Mortality	All animals	At least twice daily ^a (beginning and end of working day) beginning upon allocation through release	Animals will be observed within their cage unless necessary for identification or confirmation of possible findings.
Clinical Observations	All animals	Animals will be observed at least once daily in each period during treatment and blood sample collection.	Animals will be observed within their cage unless necessary for identification or confirmation of possible findings. For observations that cannot be attributed to an individual animal due to social housing (e.g., watery feces), the observation will be recorded to each animal in the socialized group.
Individual Body Weights	All animals	On the day of each dosing. In order to monitor the health status, animals may be weighed more often.	Animals will be individually weighed.

^a Except on days of allocation and release where frequency will be at least once daily.

11. BIOANALYSIS AND PHARMACOKINETIC EVALUATION**11.1. Bioanalytical Sample Collection**

Samples will be collected from all animals at the following timepoints:

Period 1 (IV): 0.083 (5 min), 0.25 (15 min), 0.5 (30 min), 1, 2, 4, 8, and 24 hours after dose administration.

Appendix 1

Period 2 (PO): 0.5 (30 min), 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, and 24 hours after dose administration.

Method/Comments:	Vena cava cranialis puncture
Volume (mL) :	1.0 mL Additional blood samples may be obtained (e.g., due to sample quality) if permissible sampling frequency and blood volume are not exceeded.
Anticoagulant:	K ₂ EDTA
Special Requirements:	Collection on ice
Theoretical number of samples:	64

If an animal is euthanized for humane reasons, a limited set of blood samples will be collected prior to euthanasia when possible, at the discretion of the Study Director.

11.2. Bioanalytical Sample Processing

The samples will be centrifuged within 30 minutes at approximately 1500g for 10 minutes at 4-8°C and the resultant plasma will be separated, transferred to duplicate uniquely labeled clear polypropylene tubes (150 µL in Aliquot A, remainder in Aliquot B), and frozen immediately over dry ice or in a ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C.

Aliquot A will be shipped on dry ice to the test site for bioanalysis (see [Attachment B](#)). The bioanalytical laboratory will be notified before shipment of the samples. Samples will be stored at the bioanalytical laboratory in a freezer set to maintain -70°C until analysis.

Aliquot B will function as a reserve sample and will remain in an ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C at Charles River Den Bosch until approval of the Study Director to ship or destroy the samples.

11.3. Bioanalytical Sample Analysis

The objective of the study phase is to determine the BDT272 concentrations in minipig plasma samples.

Bioanalysis will be performed under Test Site Study No. 20459019 using a validated LC-MS/MS method (BAM1093, Validation Study Number 20458990) and according to applicable Test Site SOPs.

Approximately 64 samples are expected to be received at the Test Site. Sample integrity will be verified upon reception and samples will be stored at approximately -70°C.

Samples will be analyzed after reception of all available study samples.

Re-analysis may occur for analytical reasons (e.g. run out of acceptance criteria, ALOQ results, BLOQ due to dilution, analytical issue, inappropriate IS response) or for confirmatory purpose (group control) or other re-analysis following written information from the Study Director according to Test Site's procedures..

The run will be accepted or rejected according to the Test Site SOPs.

BDT272 concentrations (ng/mL of minipig plasma) will be sent to the Study Director and the Sponsor as QC'd results.

Appendix 1**11.4. Pharmacokinetic Evaluation**

A noncompartmental analysis will be used for parameter estimation using Phoenix pharmacokinetic software. For BDT272 in plasma the extravascular or IV bolus model will be used for parameter estimation. All parameters will be generated from BDT272 individual concentrations whenever practical.

PK parameters will be generated using the concentration units provided by the bioanalytical laboratory. Concentration values that are below the limit of quantitation will be treated as zero for the purposes of PK data analysis.

Parameters to be Estimated

Parameter	Description of Parameter
t_{max}	The time at which the maximum concentration was observed.
C_0	The theoretical concentration at time zero, after intravenous dosing only.
C_0/Dose	The C_0 divided by the dose administered, after intravenous dosing only.
C_{max}	The maximum observed concentration measured, after oral administration only.
C_{max}/Dose	The C_{max} divided by the dose administered, after oral administration only.
$AUC_{t_{last}}$	The area under the concentration versus time curve from the start of dose administration to the last observed quantifiable concentration calculated using the linear trapezoidal linear interpolation method.
$AUC_{t_{last}}/\text{Dose}$	The $AUC_{t_{last}}$ divided by the dose administered.
t_{last}	The time after dosing at which the last quantifiable concentration was observed.

Based on the data, additional secondary parameters may be determined, if appropriate.

Secondary Parameter Abbreviations

Parameter	Description of Parameter
$t_{1/2}$	Terminal half life
AUC_{0-inf}	Area under the concentration-time curve from time zero extrapolated to infinity. Only determined from single dose data, if appropriate.
AUC_{0-inf}/Dose	The AUC_{0-inf} normalized for dose.
Cl	Total body clearance of parent test material, after intravenous dosing only.
V_z	Volume of distribution of parent test material based on the terminal elimination phase, after intravenous dosing only.
Cl/F	Total body clearance of parent test material divided by the fraction of dose absorbed, after oral administration only.
V_z/F	Volume of distribution of parent test material based on the terminal elimination phase divided by the fraction of dose absorbed.
F	Absolute oral bioavailability of the parent test material in the test system

Partial AUCs (between 2 defined sample times), and corresponding dose-normalized values, may be derived and reported to aid interpretation. Descriptive statistics (e.g., number, arithmetic mean, median, standard deviation, coefficient of variation) will be reported as deemed appropriate.

PK table and graphs will also be generated.

12. TERMINAL PROCEDURES

Animals will not be necropsied, and will be returned to the Test Facility animal pool.

Appendix 1**13. COMPUTERIZED SYSTEMS**

The following computerized systems may be used in the study. The actual critical computerized systems used will be specified in the Final Report. The implemented paper and electronic systems are fit for the integrity of the study data.

Computerized Systems

System name	Description of Data Collected and/or Analyzed
Provantis	In-life; Test Material receipt, accountability and/or formulation activities
Deviation Information Library	Deviations
M-Files®	Reporting and collection of 21 CFR Part 11 compliant signature
REES Centron	Temperature and humidity (animal and laboratory facilities) data collection
Dispense	Test material receipt, accountability and/or formulation activities
Analyst	LC-MS/MS instrument control, data acquisition and chromatogram peak integration (Bioanalysis)
DocuSign™	Collection of 21 CFR Part 11 compliant signature
Watson® LIMS software (Thermo Electron, Philadelphia, PA)	Sample and data management including regression, calculation and statistical calculations. (Bioanalysis)
Oceasoft	Environmental Monitoring System
Phoenix WinNonlin	Non-compartmental analysis and descriptive statistics (Pharmacokinetic evaluation)

Data for parameters not required by Study Plan, which are automatically generated by analytical devices used will be retained on file but not reported. Statistical analysis results that are generated by the program but are not required by Study Plan and/or are not scientifically relevant will be retained on file but will not be included in the tabulations.

14. REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

This study is not within the scope of regulations governing the conduct of nonclinical laboratory studies and is not intended to comply with such regulations.

15. AMENDMENTS AND DEVIATIONS

Changes to the approved Study Plan shall be made in the form of an amendment, which will be signed and dated by the Study Director. Every reasonable effort will be made to discuss any necessary Study Plan changes in advance with the Sponsor. The Study Director will notify the Sponsor of deviations that may result in a significant impact on the study as soon as possible.

16. RETENTION AND DISPOSITION OF RECORDS AND SAMPLES

All applicable study-specific raw data, electronic data, documentation, Study Plan, retained samples and specimens, and Final Report will be archived at finalization of the report. All materials generated by Charles River from this study will be transferred to a Charles River archive. At least 2 years after issue of the Final Report, the Sponsor will be contacted.

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Records to be maintained will include, but will not be limited to, documentation and data for the following:

- Study Plan, Study Plan amendments, and deviations
- Study schedule
- Study-related correspondence
- Test system receipt, health, and husbandry
- Test material receipt, identification, and preparation
- In-life measurements and observations
- Bioanalytical sample collection and evaluation
- Pharmacokinetic evaluation

All study-specific raw data and documentation from this study phase will be archived at the Test Site, except files stored on M-Files® that will be archived at the Charles River Laboratories facility location in Wilmington, MA. Two years after issue of the final phase report, the Sponsor will be contacted to determine the disposition of materials associated with the study. This will include, but not be restricted to:

- Correspondence
- Study-specific data generated from the bioanalytical phase of the study
- Copy of the draft and final bioanalytical phase reports

Disposition of residual/retained analytical samples will be as described in the table below.

Disposition of Residual/Retained Samples

Sample Type	Disposition	Schedule
Bioanalytical (CR-STN)	Discard or Archive or Return to Sponsor	A sample disposal form will be submitted to the sponsor and to the Study Director. Samples will be disposed of, retained on site or transferred externally according to the written instruction from the sponsor and from the study director.

17. REPORTING

An Abbreviated Summary Draft Report will be prepared following completion of the study and will be finalized following consultation with the Sponsor. The report will include all information necessary to provide a complete and accurate description of the experimental methods and results and any circumstances that may have affected the quality or integrity of the study.

The Sponsor will receive an electronic version of the Draft Report. The Final Report will be provided in Adobe Acrobat PDF format (hyperlinked and searchable). The PDF document will be created from native electronic files to the extent possible, including text and tables generated by the Test Facility. Report components not available in native electronic files and/or original signature pages will be scanned and converted to PDF image files for incorporation.

Appendix 1

Reports should be finalized within 6 months of issue of the Draft Report. If the Sponsor has not provided comments to the report within 6 months of draft issue, the report will be finalized by the Test Facility unless other arrangements are made by the Sponsor.

18. JUSTIFICATIONS AND GUIDELINES

18.1. Justification of Test System and Number of Animals

The Göttingen minipig was chosen as the animal model for this study as it is an accepted nonrodent species for nonclinical toxicity test by regulatory agencies.

At this time, studies in laboratory animals provide the best available basis for extrapolation to humans and are required to support regulatory submissions. Acceptable models that do not use live animals currently do not exist.

The total number of animals to be used in this study is considered to be the minimum required to properly characterize the effects of the test material and has been designed such that it does not require an unnecessary number of animals to accomplish its objectives.

18.2. Justification of Route and Dose Levels

The oral route of exposure was selected because this is the intended route of human exposure. The intravenous route of exposure was selected as it provides 100% bioavailability.

The dose levels were selected based on pharmacokinetic studies and toxicological studies in rats (Studies No. 20335882 and 20335861) and a pharmacokinetic study in dog (No. 2033588), performed by Charles River Laboratories, and pharmacological studies performed by the Sponsor. In the rat, a dose of 5 mg/kg given by oral route achieved a plasma C_{max} value of 136 ng/mL (374 nM). In the Maximal Tolerated Dose-Range Finding study, a dose of 130 mg/kg, administered during 14 days, was well tolerated in the rat. In the dog, a dose of 5 mg/kg given by oral route did not produce apparent adverse effects and achieved a plasma C_{max} value of 273 ng/mL (752 nM). Pharmacological studies indicate that the maximal effective dose achieved a C_{max} value of ~138 nM. Assuming that the pharmacokinetics in the minipig will be similar to that in the dog, a dose of 2 mg/kg given orally will achieve a C_{max} that is well above the equivalent active dose. Given the results in rat and dog, this dose is not likely to produce adverse effects.

The dose of 0.5 mg/kg given by intravenous route was selected accordingly, as being not likely to produce adverse effects, even in the case plasma exposure by intravenous route exceeds that of oral route.

18.3. Guidelines for Study

The design of this study was based on the study objective(s) and the overall product development strategy for the test material.

19. ANIMAL WELFARE

This Study Plan was reviewed and agreed by the Animal Welfare Body of Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V. within the framework of Appendix 3 of project license AVD23600202216274 approved by the Central Authority for Scientific Procedures on Animals (CCD) as required by the Dutch Act on Animal Experimentation (December 2014).

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Animals showing pain, distress or discomfort, which is considered not transient in nature or is likely to become more severe, will be sacrificed for humane reasons based on OECD guidance document on the recognition, assessment, and use of clinical signs as humane endpoints for experimental animals used in safety evaluation (ENV/JM/MONO/2000/7).

By approving this Study Plan, the Sponsor affirms that this study is required by a relevant government regulatory agency and that it does not unnecessarily duplicate any previous experiments.

Appendix 1**ATTACHMENT A**

Distribution List

Electronic copies will be supplied unless otherwise specified below.

Version	Recipient	
Original	Study Director	
1 Copy	Sponsor Representative / Study Monitor	
1 Copy	Formulations	Tsfher;
1 Copy	Veterinarian	Veterinariangither;
1 Copy	Study Assistants	Sagit;
1 Copy	Principal Investigator Bioanalysis	camille.tanguy@crl.com;
1 Copy	Coordinating Biotechnician	van Dijk, J; Verhagen, L;
1 Copy	Clinical Pathology	Her/clinical pathology;

Appendix 1**ATTACHMENT B**

Shipment of Samples and Study Records

Matrix	Purpose	Day/ Week/ Aliquot	Proposed Shipment Date	Conditions for Shipment	Recipient/Address
Plasma	Bioanalysis	All samples, Aliquot A	28 Aug 2023	On dry ice, with temperature logger	Attention To Camille Tanguy Charles River Laboratoires Saint-Nazaire Rue Graham Bell, ZI de Brais BP 40309 44605 SAINT-NAZAIRE Cedex France Tel: +33 2 28 54 31 29 E-mail: camille.tanguy@crl.com

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AMENDMENT APPROVAL

I hereby confirm that I am aware of all necessary information concerning the study including GLP compliance, Study Plan, amendments, and deviations as allocated to me by management as replacement Study Director.

All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.

Appendix 1

SIGNATURE(S) FOR DOCUMENT: 20458624 - Study Plan Amend 02

TFM Approval- NGLP:	I approve the Study Director identified in this document and acknowledge the study.	
Name:	van 't Root, Moniek	
	<i>van 't Root, Moniek</i>	
		07-Sep-2023 10:24:41 (UTC+00:00)
Electronically Signed in		Timestamp

Study Director Approval:	I approve this document.	
Name:	van Pijpen, Freeke	
	<i>van Pijpen, Freeke</i>	
		07-Sep-2023 10:45:30 (UTC+00:00)
Electronically Signed in		Timestamp

Appendix 1

FINAL STUDY PLAN

Test Facility Study No. 20458624

Sponsor Reference No. BDT272-23-013

**Single Dose Pharmacokinetics of BDT272 after Oral and Intravenous
Administration in Female Göttingen Minipigs**

Non-GLP

SPONSOR:

Biodol Therapeutics
CAP Alpha
Avenue de l'Europe
34830 Clapiers
France

TEST FACILITY:

Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V.
Hambakenwetering 7
5231 DD 's-Hertogenbosch
The Netherlands

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Appendix 1**1. OBJECTIVE(S)**

The objective of this study is to investigate the pharmacokinetics of BDT272, when given orally by gavage and intravenously to female Gottingen minipigs. In addition, the possible oral bioavailability of BDT272 will be assessed.

2. PROPOSED STUDY SCHEDULE

Proposed study dates are listed below. Actual dates will be included in the Final Report.

Experimental Starting Date:	14 Aug 2023 (First date of study-specific data collection; allocation)
Experimental Completion Date:	09 Nov 2023 (Last date on which data are collected)
Initiation of Dosing:	15 Aug 2023
Completion of In-life:	23 Aug 2023 (Release of animals from study)
Administration of Test Material:	
- Period 1:	15 Aug 2023
- Period 2:	22 Aug 2023
Blood Sampling for Pharmacokinetics:	
- Period 1:	15-16 Aug 2023
- Period 2:	22-23 Aug 2023
Draft Report:	10 Nov 2023
Final Report:	Within 6 months after issuing the draft report (i.e. latest 10 May 2024)

The contributions from Principal Investigators to Study Director are proposed at the dates indicated below to allow inclusion in Draft Report.

Bioanalytical QC'd Results Available:	06 Oct 2023 (QC'd data required at this date to allow Pharmacokinetic analysis)
Pharmacokinetic Draft Report:	27 Oct 2023

3. SPONSOR

Role	Name	Contact Information
Sponsor Representative/ Study Monitor	Pierre Sokoloff	Address as cited for Sponsor Tel: +33 7 70 41 63 68 E-mail: pierre.sokoloff@biodol.eu

Appendix 1**4. RESPONSIBLE PERSONNEL**

Role/Phase	Name	Contact Information
Study Director	Freeke van Pijpen, MSc	Address as cited for Test Facility Tel: +31 73 640 6700 E-mail: freeke.vanpijpen@crl.com
Test Facility Management	Harry Emmen, MSc	Address as cited for Test Facility Tel: +31 73 640 6700 E-mail: harry.emmen@crl.com
Individual Scientist (IS)		
PK evaluation	Name will be included in the Final Report.	
Principal Investigator (PI)		
Bioanalysis	Camille Tanguy, MSc (PI)	Charles River Laboratories Saint-Nazaire 1 rue Graham Bell ZI de Brais – CS 40309 44605 Saint-Nazaire Cedex France Tel : +33 2 28 54 31 29 E-mail: camille.tanguy@crl.com
	Solenn Vincent, MSc (Deputy PI)	Address as cited for Bioanalysis Test Site Tel : +33 2 51 10 10 93 E-mail: solenn.vincent@crl.com

Each IS and PI is required to report all deviations or other circumstances that could affect the quality or integrity of the study to the Study Director in a timely manner for authorization/acknowledgement. The PI of Bioanalysis will provide an Excel and the IS of the Pharmacokinetic Evaluation will provide a report addressing their assigned phase of the study, which will be included as an appendix to the Final Report.

The IS Phase Report will include the following:

- A listing of critical computerized systems used in the conduct and/or interpretation of the assigned study phase

5. TEST MATERIALS**5.1. Test Material Characterization**

A Certificate of Analysis or equivalent documentation will be provided for inclusion in the Final Report (if available).

5.2. Test Material Identification**5.2.1. Test Material**

Identification:	BDT272
Batch (Lot) Number:	L22024-A
Expiry Date:	07 October 2023 (retest date)
Physical Description:	Off-white powder
Purity/Composition:	100% UPLC

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Storage Conditions: Room temperature set to maintain 21°C protected from light desiccated

Additional information

Test Facility Test Material Number: 213138/F

Purity/Composition Correction Factor: No correction factor required

Test Material Handling: Use amber glassware or wrap container in aluminum foil

Stability in vehicle:

50% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS + 0.5% Tween 80 Stability for at least 24 hours at room temperature under normal laboratory light conditions and 8 days in the refrigerator is confirmed over the concentration range 1 to 50 mg/mL (solutions, 500 mL bulk volume), Test Facility Study No. 20397039

5.2.2. Vehicle – Period 1 (IV)

Identification: 15% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS

5.2.3. Vehicle – Period 2 (PO)

Identification: 50% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS + 0.5% Tween-80

5.3. Reserve Samples

For each batch (lot) of test material and if practically possible, a reserve sample will be collected and maintained under the appropriate storage conditions by the Test Facility.

5.4. Test Material Inventory and Disposition

Records of the receipt, distribution, storage, and disposition of test materials will be maintained.

5.5. Safety

The following safety instruction(s) apply to this study:

- Standard safety precautions specified in Charles River Den Bosch procedures
- Specific safety precautions are provided in the Charles River Den Bosch internal EH&S test material risk assessment

Appendix 1**6. DOSE FORMULATION AND ANALYSIS****6.1. Preparation of Formulations**

Preparation Details

Dose Formulation	Administration Dose Form	Procedure	Frequency of Preparation	Storage Conditions Set to Maintain
Period 1 (IV)	Solution	The test material is weighed and finely grinded using a mortar and pestle. Vehicle is then added in small portions with continuous grinding (using mortar and pestle) until a fine homogenous paste is created. Subsequently, the rest of the vehicle is added. The formulation is then homogenized to visually acceptable levels.	On the day before dose administration.	4°C, protected from light
Period 2 (PO)	Solution/Suspension	The formulation for IV administration will be filtered using a 0.2 µM filter prior to dose administration.	On the day before dose administration.	4°C, protected from light

Adjustments will be made for specific gravity of the vehicle. No correction will be made for the purity/composition of the test material.

Any residual volumes from each dosing occasion will be discarded unless otherwise requested by the Study Director.

6.2. Sample Collection and Analysis

Analysis of test material in vehicle for concentration, stability, homogeneity will not be performed, however, to limit the impact, the test material preparation will be performed with approved procedures and documented in detail. Formulations will be visually inspected for homogeneity prior to use and all formulations will be used within 6 hours after removal from the refrigerator.

7. TEST SYSTEM

Species: Minipig
 Strain: Göttingen
 Animal Condition: Outbred, microbiologically defined, non-naïve
 Animal Supplier: Ellegaard Göttingen minipigs, Sorø Landevej 302, DK-4261 Dalmose, Denmark
 Treatment History: The non-naïve animals were last used in the following studies: Test Facility Study No. 20420875, 20420876, or 20432938. Animals were not used after 16 May 2023. Based on the half-lives of the test

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materials dosed in previous studies, the wash-out period is considered to be sufficient.

Number of Females: 4
Target Age at the
Initiation of Dosing: 10 to 11 months
Target Weight at the
Initiation of Dosing: 15 to 18 kg

The actual age and weight of the animals at the initiation of dosing will be listed in the Final Report.

7.1. Animal Identification

Method: Each animal will be identified using an ear tag and/or subcutaneously implanted electronic identification chip.

7.2. Environmental Acclimation

The animals selected for this study originate from the animal pool housed at the Test Facility, therefore these animals are already acclimated to the Test Facility toxicology accommodation and are directly available for the commencement of dosing.

7.3. Selection, Assignment, and Disposition of Animals

Selection: The females selected for the study will be assigned to Group 1.
Disposition: The disposition of all animals will be documented in the study records.

8. HUSBANDRY**8.1. Housing**

Housing: Group housed (up to 4 animals).
These housing conditions will be maintained unless deemed inappropriate by the Study Director and/or Clinical Veterinarian. The room(s) in which the animals will be kept will be documented in the study records.
Animals will be socially housed with the exception of times when they are separated for designated study procedures/activities.

Caging: Stainless steel cages and sterilized sawdust will be used as bedding material.

Cage Identification: Color-coded cage card indicating Test Facility Study No., group, animal/tattoo number(s).

Appendix 1**8.2. Animal Enrichment**

For psychological/environmental enrichment, animals will be provided with items such as a rug and balls, except when interrupted by study procedures/activities.

8.3. Environmental Conditions

The targeted conditions for animal room environment will be as follows:

Temperature:	15 to 21°C
Humidity:	30 to 70%
Light Cycle:	12-hours light and 12-hours dark (except during designated procedures) (nightlight during the night period)
Ventilation:	Ten or more air changes per hour

8.4. Food

Diet:	KLIBA 3000PSS15 (Kaiseraugst, Switzerland)
Type:	Kibble (alternate diet may be provided on individual animal basis as warranted as approved by the Study Director).
Frequency/Ration:	An appropriate ration of feed (based on body weights, details will be recorded in the raw data) will be offered divided over two daily portions at the beginning and end of the working day.

During the night prior to the days of dosing, animals will be fasted, but water will be available. On the days of dosing, the first daily food ration will be available approximately 2 hour after dosing.

In addition, minipigs may be rewarded with apple juice, marshmallows or raisins during training and handling, when necessary.

Analysis:	Results of analysis for nutritional components and environmental contaminants are provided by the supplier and are on file at the Test Facility. It is considered that there are no known contaminants in the feed that would interfere with the objectives of the study.
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8.5. Water

Type:	Municipal tap water.
Frequency/Ration:	Freely available to each animal via an automatic watering system (except during designated procedures).
Analysis:	Periodic analysis of the water is performed, and results of these analyses are on file at the Test Facility. It is considered that there are no known contaminants in the water that could interfere with the outcome of the study.

Appendix 1**8.6. Veterinary Care**

Veterinary care will be available throughout the course of the study and animals will be examined by the veterinary staff as warranted by clinical signs or other changes. In the event that animals show signs of illness or distress, the responsible veterinarian may make initial recommendations about treatment of the animal(s) and/or alteration of study procedures, which must be approved by the Study Director. Treatment of the animal(s) for minor injuries or ailments may be approved without prior consultation with the Sponsor representative when such treatment does not impact fulfillment of the study objectives. If the condition of the animal(s) warrants significant therapeutic intervention or alterations in study procedures, the Sponsor representative will be contacted, when possible, to discuss appropriate action. If the condition of the animal(s) is such that emergency measures must be taken, the Study Director and/or attending veterinarian will attempt to consult with the Sponsor representative prior to responding to the medical crisis, but the Study Director and/or veterinarian has authority to act immediately at his/her discretion to alleviate suffering. The Sponsor representative will be fully informed of any such events.

9. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Period ^b	Test Material Id.	Dose Level (mg/kg)	Dose Volume ^a (mL/kg)	Dose Concentration (mg/mL)	Dose Route	Number of Animals	Animal Numbers
						Females	Females
1	BDT272	0.5	0.5	1	IV	4	1-4
2		2	1	2	PO		

Id.= identification.

^a Based on the most recent body weight measurement.

^b There will be a wash-out period of one week between the consecutive periods

9.1. Administration of Test Materials**9.1.1. Period 1 – IV Bolus**

Dose Route: Intravenous (slow bolus) injection into the ear vein

Treatment: Once

Frequency:

Treatment Duration: Single dose

Method: The day of dosing will be designated as Day 1. The dose formulations will be stirred continuously during dosing. The dose volume for each animal will be based on the most recent body weight measurement. The animals will be temporarily placed in a sling-type restraining device during injection. The dose will be given using a flexible catheter with butterfly needle connected to a disposable syringe. The dose will be administered as quickly as practically possible and the exact dosing time in seconds will be recorded. The time of ending the intravenous bolus injection will be designated as time 0.

Dose pot identification via Provantis will be used as additional check to verify the dosing procedure according to Standard Operating Procedures.

Appendix 1**9.1.2. Period 2 – Oral Gavage**

Dose Route: Oral gavage

Treatment: Once

Frequency:

Treatment Duration: Single dose

Method: The dose formulations will be stirred continuously during dosing. The animals will be temporarily placed in a v-trog restraining device during dosing. The doses will be given using a flexible catheter. Each dose will be followed by a tap water flush of approximately 20 mL.

Dose pot identification via Provantis will be used as additional check to verify the dosing procedure according to Standard Operating Procedures.

10. IN-LIFE PROCEDURES, OBSERVATIONS, AND MEASUREMENTS

General In-life Assessments –Study Animals

Parameter	Population(s)	Frequency (minimum required)	Comments
Mortality	All animals	At least twice daily ^a (beginning and end of working day) beginning upon allocation through release	Animals will be observed within their cage unless necessary for identification or confirmation of possible findings.
Clinical Observations	All animals	Animals will be observed at least once daily in each period during treatment and blood sample collection.	Animals will be observed within their cage unless necessary for identification or confirmation of possible findings. For observations that cannot be attributed to an individual animal due to social housing (e.g., watery feces), the observation will be recorded to each animal in the socialized group.
Individual Body Weights	All animals	On the day of each dosing. In order to monitor the health status, animals may be weighed more often.	Animals will be individually weighed.

^a Except on days of allocation and release where frequency will be at least once daily.

11. BIOANALYSIS AND PHARMACOKINETIC EVALUATION**11.1. Bioanalytical Sample Collection**

Samples will be collected from all animals at the following timepoints:

Period 1 (IV): 0.083 (5 min), 0.25 (15 min), 0.5 (30 min), 1, 2, 4, 8, and 24 hours after dose administration.

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Period 2 (PO): 0.5 (30 min), 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, and 24 hours after dose administration.

Method/Comments:	Vena cava cranialis puncture
Volume (mL) :	1.0 mL Additional blood samples may be obtained (e.g., due to sample quality) if permissible sampling frequency and blood volume are not exceeded.
Anticoagulant:	K ₂ EDTA
Special Requirements:	Collection on ice
Theoretical number of samples:	64

If an animal is euthanized for humane reasons, a limited set of blood samples will be collected prior to euthanasia when possible, at the discretion of the Study Director.

11.2. Bioanalytical Sample Processing

The samples will be centrifuged within 30 minutes at approximately 1500g for 10 minutes at 4-8°C and the resultant plasma will be separated, transferred to duplicate uniquely labeled clear polypropylene tubes (150 µL in Aliquot A, remainder in Aliquot B), and frozen immediately over dry ice or in a ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C.

Aliquot A will be shipped on dry ice to the test site for bioanalysis (see [Attachment B](#)). The bioanalytical laboratory will be notified before shipment of the samples. Samples will be stored at the bioanalytical laboratory in a freezer set to maintain -70°C until analysis.

Aliquot B will function as a reserve sample and will remain in an ultra-low freezer set to maintain -80°C at Charles River Den Bosch until approval of the Study Director to ship or destroy the samples.

11.3. Bioanalytical Sample Analysis

The objective of the study phase is to determine the BDT272 concentrations in minipig plasma samples.

Bioanalysis will be performed under Test Site Study No. 20459019 using a validated LC-MS/MS method (BAM1093, Validation Study Number 20458990) and according to applicable Test Site SOPs.

Approximately 64 samples are expected to be received at the Test Site. Sample integrity will be verified upon reception and samples will be stored at approximately -70°C.

Samples will be analyzed after reception of all available study samples.

Re-analysis may occur for analytical reasons (e.g. run out of acceptance criteria, ALOQ results, BLOQ due to dilution, analytical issue, inappropriate IS response) or for confirmatory purpose (group control) or other re-analysis following written information from the Study Director according to Test Site's procedures..

The run will be accepted or rejected according to the Test Site SOPs.

BDT272 concentrations (ng/mL of minipig plasma) will be sent to the Study Director and the Sponsor as QC'd results.

Appendix 1**11.4. Pharmacokinetic Evaluation**

A noncompartmental analysis will be used for parameter estimation using Phoenix pharmacokinetic software. For BDT272 in plasma the extravascular or IV bolus model will be used for parameter estimation. All parameters will be generated from BDT272 individual concentrations whenever practical.

PK parameters will be generated using the concentration units provided by the bioanalytical laboratory. Concentration values that are below the limit of quantitation will be treated as zero for the purposes of PK data analysis.

Parameters to be Estimated

Parameter	Description of Parameter
t_{max}	The time at which the maximum concentration was observed.
C_0	The theoretical concentration at time zero, after intravenous dosing only.
C_0/Dose	The C_0 divided by the dose administered, after intravenous dosing only.
C_{max}	The maximum observed concentration measured, after oral administration only.
C_{max}/Dose	The C_{max} divided by the dose administered, after oral administration only.
$AUC_{t_{last}}$	The area under the concentration versus time curve from the start of dose administration to the last observed quantifiable concentration calculated using the linear trapezoidal linear interpolation method.
$AUC_{t_{last}}/\text{Dose}$	The $AUC_{t_{last}}$ divided by the dose administered.
t_{last}	The time after dosing at which the last quantifiable concentration was observed.

Based on the data, additional secondary parameters may be determined, if appropriate.

Secondary Parameter Abbreviations

Parameter	Description of Parameter
$t_{1/2}$	Terminal half life
AUC_{0-inf}	Area under the concentration-time curve from time zero extrapolated to infinity. Only determined from single dose data, if appropriate.
AUC_{0-inf}/Dose	The AUC_{0-inf} normalized for dose.
Cl	Total body clearance of parent test material, after intravenous dosing only.
V_z	Volume of distribution of parent test material based on the terminal elimination phase, after intravenous dosing only.
Cl/F	Total body clearance of parent test material divided by the fraction of dose absorbed, after oral administration only.
V_z/F	Volume of distribution of parent test material based on the terminal elimination phase divided by the fraction of dose absorbed.
F	Absolute oral bioavailability of the parent test material in the test system

Partial AUCs (between 2 defined sample times), and corresponding dose-normalized values, may be derived and reported to aid interpretation. Descriptive statistics (e.g., number, arithmetic mean, median, standard deviation, coefficient of variation) will be reported as deemed appropriate.

PK table and graphs will also be generated.

12. TERMINAL PROCEDURES

Animals will not be necropsied, and will be returned to the Test Facility animal pool.

Appendix 1**13. COMPUTERIZED SYSTEMS**

The following computerized systems may be used in the study. The actual critical computerized systems used will be specified in the Final Report. The implemented paper and electronic systems are fit for the integrity of the study data.

Computerized Systems

System name	Description of Data Collected and/or Analyzed
Provantis	In-life; Test Material receipt, accountability and/or formulation activities
Deviation Information Library	Deviations
M-Files®	Reporting and collection of 21 CFR Part 11 compliant signature
REES Centron	Temperature and humidity (animal and laboratory facilities) data collection
Dispense	Test material receipt, accountability and/or formulation activities
Analyst	LC-MS/MS instrument control, data acquisition and chromatogram peak integration (Bioanalysis)
DocuSign™	Collection of 21 CFR Part 11 compliant signature
Watson® LIMS software (Thermo Electron, Philadelphia, PA)	Sample and data management including regression, calculation and statistical calculations. (Bioanalysis)
Oceasoftware	Environmental Monitoring System
Phoenix WinNonlin	Non-compartmental analysis and descriptive statistics (Pharmacokinetic evaluation)

Data for parameters not required by Study Plan, which are automatically generated by analytical devices used will be retained on file but not reported. Statistical analysis results that are generated by the program but are not required by Study Plan and/or are not scientifically relevant will be retained on file but will not be included in the tabulations.

14. REGULATORY COMPLIANCE

This study is not within the scope of regulations governing the conduct of nonclinical laboratory studies and is not intended to comply with such regulations.

15. AMENDMENTS AND DEVIATIONS

Changes to the approved Study Plan shall be made in the form of an amendment, which will be signed and dated by the Study Director. Every reasonable effort will be made to discuss any necessary Study Plan changes in advance with the Sponsor. The Study Director will notify the Sponsor of deviations that may result in a significant impact on the study as soon as possible.

16. RETENTION AND DISPOSITION OF RECORDS AND SAMPLES

All applicable study-specific raw data, electronic data, documentation, Study Plan, retained samples and specimens, and Final Report will be archived at finalization of the report. All materials generated by Charles River from this study will be transferred to a Charles River archive. At least 2 years after issue of the Final Report, the Sponsor will be contacted.

Appendix 1

Records to be maintained will include, but will not be limited to, documentation and data for the following:

- Study Plan, Study Plan amendments, and deviations
- Study schedule
- Study-related correspondence
- Test system receipt, health, and husbandry
- Test material receipt, identification, and preparation
- In-life measurements and observations
- Bioanalytical sample collection and evaluation
- Pharmacokinetic evaluation

All study-specific raw data and documentation from this study phase will be archived at the Test Site, except files stored on M-Files® that will be archived at the Charles River Laboratories facility location in Wilmington, MA. Two years after issue of the final phase report, the Sponsor will be contacted to determine the disposition of materials associated with the study. This will include, but not be restricted to:

- Correspondence
- Study-specific data generated from the bioanalytical phase of the study
- Copy of the draft and final bioanalytical phase reports

Disposition of residual/retained analytical samples will be as described in the table below.

Disposition of Residual/Retained Samples

Sample Type	Disposition	Schedule
Bioanalytical (CR-STN)	Discard or Archive or Return to Sponsor	A sample disposal form will be submitted to the sponsor and to the Study Director. Samples will be disposed of, retained on site or transferred externally according to the written instruction from the sponsor and from the study director.

17. REPORTING

An Abbreviated Summary Draft Report will be prepared following completion of the study and will be finalized following consultation with the Sponsor. The report will include all information necessary to provide a complete and accurate description of the experimental methods and results and any circumstances that may have affected the quality or integrity of the study.

The Sponsor will receive an electronic version of the Draft Report. The Final Report will be provided in Adobe Acrobat PDF format (hyperlinked and searchable). The PDF document will be created from native electronic files to the extent possible, including text and tables generated by the Test Facility. Report components not available in native electronic files and/or original signature pages will be scanned and converted to PDF image files for incorporation.

Appendix 1

Reports should be finalized within 6 months of issue of the Draft Report. If the Sponsor has not provided comments to the report within 6 months of draft issue, the report will be finalized by the Test Facility unless other arrangements are made by the Sponsor.

18. JUSTIFICATIONS AND GUIDELINES

18.1. Justification of Test System and Number of Animals

The Göttingen minipig was chosen as the animal model for this study as it is an accepted nonrodent species for nonclinical toxicity test by regulatory agencies.

At this time, studies in laboratory animals provide the best available basis for extrapolation to humans and are required to support regulatory submissions. Acceptable models that do not use live animals currently do not exist.

The total number of animals to be used in this study is considered to be the minimum required to properly characterize the effects of the test material and has been designed such that it does not require an unnecessary number of animals to accomplish its objectives.

18.2. Justification of Route and Dose Levels

The oral route of exposure was selected because this is the intended route of human exposure. The intravenous route of exposure was selected as it provides 100% bioavailability.

The dose levels were selected based on pharmacokinetic studies and toxicological studies in rats (Studies No. 20335882 and 20335861) and a pharmacokinetic study in dog (No. 2033588), performed by Charles River Laboratories, and pharmacological studies performed by the Sponsor. In the rat, a dose of 5 mg/kg given by oral route achieved a plasma C_{max} value of 136 ng/mL (374 nM). In the Maximal Tolerated Dose-Range Finding study, a dose of 130 mg/kg, administered during 14 days, was well tolerated in the rat. In the dog, a dose of 5 mg/kg given by oral route did not produce apparent adverse effects and achieved a plasma C_{max} value of 273 ng/mL (752 nM). Pharmacological studies indicate that the maximal effective dose achieved a C_{max} value of ~138 nM. Assuming that the pharmacokinetics in the minipig will be similar to that in the dog, a dose of 2 mg/kg given orally will achieve a C_{max} that is well above the equivalent active dose. Given the results in rat and dog, this dose is not likely to produce adverse effects.

The dose of 0.5 mg/kg given by intravenous route was selected accordingly, as being not likely to produce adverse effects, even in the case plasma exposure by intravenous route exceeds that of oral route.

18.3. Guidelines for Study

The design of this study was based on the study objective(s) and the overall product development strategy for the test material.

19. ANIMAL WELFARE

This Study Plan was reviewed and agreed by the Animal Welfare Body of Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V. within the framework of Appendix 3 of project license AVD23600202216274 approved by the Central Authority for Scientific Procedures on Animals (CCD) as required by the Dutch Act on Animal Experimentation (December 2014).

Appendix 1

Animals showing pain, distress or discomfort, which is considered not transient in nature or is likely to become more severe, will be sacrificed for humane reasons based on OECD guidance document on the recognition, assessment, and use of clinical signs as humane endpoints for experimental animals used in safety evaluation (ENV/JM/MONO/2000/7).

By approving this Study Plan, the Sponsor affirms that this study is required by a relevant government regulatory agency and that it does not unnecessarily duplicate any previous experiments.

Appendix 1**ATTACHMENT A**

Distribution List

Electronic copies will be supplied unless otherwise specified below.

Version	Recipient	
Original	Study Director	
1 Copy	Sponsor Representative / Study Monitor	
1 Copy	Formulations	Tsfher;
1 Copy	Veterinarian	Veterinariangither;
1 Copy	Study Assistants	Sagit;
1 Copy	Principal Investigator Bioanalysis	camille.tanguy@crl.com;
1 Copy	Coordinating Biotechnician	van Dijk, J; Verhagen, L;
1 Copy	Clinical Pathology	Her/clinical pathology;

Appendix 1**ATTACHMENT B**

Shipment of Samples and Study Records

Matrix	Purpose	Day/ Week/ Aliquot	Proposed Shipment Date	Conditions for Shipment	Recipient/Address
Plasma	Bioanalysis	All samples, Aliquot A	28 Aug 2023	On dry ice, with temperature logger	Attention To Camille Tanguy Charles River Laboratoires Saint-Nazaire Rue Graham Bell, ZI de Brais BP 40309 44605 SAINT-NAZAIRE Cedex France Tel: +33 2 28 54 31 29 E-mail: camille.tanguy@crl.com

Appendix 1

SPONSOR APPROVAL

The Study Plan was approved by the Sponsor by e-mail on the date designated below. The correspondence giving approval will be archived, as appropriate with other Sponsor communications.

08 Aug 2023

Date of Sponsor Approval

Appendix 1

TEST FACILITY APPROVAL

The signature below indicates that Test Facility Management approves the Study Director identified in this Study Plan and acknowledges the study.

All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.

Appendix 1

SIGNATURE(S) FOR DOCUMENT: 20458624 - Study Plan

TFM Approval- NGLP:	I approve the Study Director identified in this document and acknowledge the study.	
Name:	Wenker, Mira	
		09-Aug-2023 09:59:38 (UTC+00:00)
Electronically Signed in		Timestamp

Study Director Approval:	I approve this document.	
Name:	van Pijpen, Freeke	
		09-Aug-2023 10:01:09 (UTC+00:00)
Electronically Signed in		Timestamp

Appendix 2

Test Material Characterization
20458624

ANALYSIS CERTIFICATE Nb : BA_110423_1

p.1/2

PRODUCT	BDT272	TYPE	Final Product
Project:	L22024	Supplier:	ROOWIN
Batch Nb:	L22024-A	N° CAS:	NA
Sample Nb:	L22024091901	Manufacturing date:	07/04/2023
Storage conditions:	Ambiant temperature	Retest date:	07/10/2023

ANALYSIS	METHOD / REVISION	SPEC.	RESULTS	OBSERVATIONS	REFERENCE
Identification					
Appearance	Visual Method -	Reported Result	Off-white powder	-	-
¹ H-NMR	AN/2010/MAS/919 003	In accordance with structure	In accordance	DMSO-d6	L22024-A 1H
Mass spectrometry	AN/2014/MAS/1635 000	In accordance with structure	In accordance	[M+H] ⁺ : 364 m/z [M+2H] ²⁺ : 183 m/z (ESI ⁺)	RA_L22024091901_MS
IR Spectrometry	AN/2021/MAS/2683 001	In accordance with standard	In accordance	ATR	RA_L22024091901_IR
Identification by HPLC	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	Retention time of the compound similar to retention time of the standard (difference must not be greater than 5.0%)	In progress	-	-
XRPD	X-Ray diffraction -	Reported Result	In progress	-	-
Titration					
Water Content (by Karl-Fischer)	AN/2012/MAS/1302 003	Reported Result	0.2%	w/w, average of 3 determinations	RA_L22024091901_KF
HPLC analysis					
Purity (%AUC)	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	-	99.93%	235nm; average of 3 determinations	RA_L22024091901_HPLC
Total impurity	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	≤ 2%	0%		
Specified impurities	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	Reported Result	Not detected		
Individual unspecified impurity (RRT 1.17)	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	Reported Result	0.07%		
Assay	AN/2023/MAS/3024 000	Reported Result	In progress	-	-
GC analysis: Residual solvents					
Dichloromethane (DCM)	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 600ppm	In progress	FID	-
Tert-Butanol (tBuOH)	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 3500ppm	In progress		
Tetrahydrofuran (THF)	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 720ppm	In progress		
Cyclohexane	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 3880ppm	In progress		
Ethanol (EtOH)	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 5000ppm	In progress		
Tert-Butyl methyl Ether (MTBE)	AN/2014/MAS/1562 001	≤ 5000ppm	In progress		

Appendix 2**Test Material Characterization**
20458624**ANALYSIS CERTIFICATE Nb : BA_I10423_I**

p.2/2

PRODUCT	BDT272	TYPE	Final Product
Project:	L22024	Supplier:	ROOWIN
Batch Nb:	L22024-A	N° CAS:	NA
Sample Nb:	L22024091901	Manufacturing date:	07/04/2023
Storage conditions:	Ambiant temperature	Retest date:	07/10/2023

ANALYSIS	METHOD / REVISION	SPEC.	RESULTS	OBSERVATIONS	REFERENCE
Elemental analysis					
Cadmium	AN/2023/MAS/3029 000	< 0.5ppm	In progress	-	-
Arsenic	AN/2023/MAS/3029 000	< 1.5ppm	In progress	-	-
Lead	AN/2023/MAS/3029 000	< 0.5ppm	In progress	-	-
Mercury	AN/2023/MAS/3029 000	< 3ppm	In progress	-	-
Palladium	AN/2023/MAS/3029 000	< 10ppm	< 10ppm	ICP-AES	RA_L22024091901_ICP
Structural analysis					
DSC	AN/2010/MAS/953 004	Reported result	Endotherm I : Onset: 209.45°C	-	RA_L22024091901_DSC

Checking:	Laurine DUCLOS	Approval:	Julien MICHAUX
Comment:	V000 – CoA interim	Comment:	/
Date:	12/04/2023	Approved on:	12/04/2023
Visa:			

Appendix 3

Explanation Page

20458624

General

Note: The days of Period 2 are reported as relative to day 1 of Period 1.
Period 2 is represented by dosing day 8.

Mortality

Note: Since no mortality occurred during the study, no table is published in this report.

Clinical Observations

Note: Only positive findings are presented. Since there are no observations for any animals on any time point, no table is published in this report.

Appendix 4

20-Sep-2023 08:04:35

Individual Body Weights

20458624

Sex: Female Bodyweight (kg)

Group 1	Day(s) Relative to Start Date	
	1	8
1	20.3	21.9
2	20.0	21.2
3	17.6	18.4
4	19.7	19.9
Mean	19.40	20.35
SD	1.22	1.54
N	4	4

Appendix 5

Final Report

Study Phase: Pharmacokinetics

Test Facility Study No. 20458624

Sponsor Reference No. BDT272-23-013

TEST FACILITY:

Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V.
Hambakenwetering 7
5231 DD 's-Hertogenbosch
The Netherlands

Appendix 5

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Appendix 5

REPORT APPROVAL

All electronic signatures appear at the end of the document upon finalization.

Appendix 5**LIST OF PARAMETER ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS**

AUC	Area under the curve
AUC% _{extrap}	Extrapolated area under the drug concentration versus time curve expressed as percent of the total AUC _{0-inf}
AUC _{all}	Area under the concentration-time curve from time 0 to the last time point (equivalent to and reported as AUC _{tlast})
AUC _{0-inf}	Area under the concentration-time curve from time 0 extrapolated to infinity
AUC _{0-inf} /Dose	AUC _{0-inf} divided by the dose administered
AUC _{tlast}	Area under the concentration-time curve from time 0 to the time of the final quantifiable sample
AUC _{tlast} /Dose	AUC _{tlast} divided by the dose administered
C ₀	Theoretical concentration at time 0 (IV bolus dosing only)
C ₀ /Dose	C ₀ divided by the dose administered
C _{max}	Maximum observed concentration (Oral dosing only)
C _{max} /Dose	C _{max} divided by the dose administered (Oral dosing only)
Cl	Total body clearance (IV administration only)
Cl/F	Total body clearance divided by the fraction of dose absorbed (Oral dosing only)
%F	Absolute bioavailability, expressed as a percent, calculated using AUC _{0-inf} /Dose and AUC _{tlast} /Dose
RSQ, R ² , or r-squared	Goodness of fit statistic for the terminal elimination phase
t _{1/2}	Terminal half life
t _{last}	Time of final quantifiable concentration
t _{max}	Time of maximum observed sample concentration (Oral dosing only)
V _z	Volume of distribution based on the terminal elimination phase (IV administration only)
V _z /F	Volume of distribution based on the terminal elimination phase divided by the fraction of dose absorbed (Oral dosing only)

Appendix 5**1. RESPONSIBLE PERSONNEL**

Individual Scientist, Pharmacokinetics

Nicole van Wijk, MSc

Charles River Laboratories Den Bosch B.V.

2. INTRODUCTION

This report describes the plasma pharmacokinetics (PK) of BDT272 in female Göttingen minipigs following single dose intravenous (IV) and oral (PO) administration.

For the work detailed in this report, the PK phase start date was 06 Oct 2023 and the PK phase completion date was 06 Oct 2023.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The experimental design is summarized in [Text Table 1](#).

Text Table 1
Experimental Design

Period ^b	Test Material	Dose Level (mg/kg)	Dose Volume ^a (mL/kg)	Dose Concentration (mg/mL)	Dose Route	No. of Animals
						Females
1	BDT272	0.5	0.5	1	IV	4
2	BDT272	2	1	2	PO	4

^a Dose volume was based on the most recent body weight measurement.

^b There was a wash-out period of one week between the consecutive periods.

The vehicle used in Period 1 was 15% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS and 50% (w/w) PEG400 in PBS + 0.5% Tween-80 in Period 2. BDT272 in their respective vehicles were administered to the appropriate animals once via IV (slow bolus) injection and once via oral gavage administration.

Blood samples were collected at 0.083 (5 minutes), 0.25 (15 minutes), 0.5 (30 minutes), 1, 2, 4, 8 and 24 hours after IV dose administration and at 0.5 (30 minutes), 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8 and 24 hours after oral dose administration.

PK blood samples were processed to plasma and analyzed for concentrations of BDT272 ([Table 4](#)) by Charles River Laboratories Saint-Nazaire, Saint-Nazaire Cedex, France.

Details on the bioanalytical method can be found in the respective appendix of the main report.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS**4.1. Study Events**

- The dosing of Animal No. 1 was interrupted for 23 seconds. The total dose was administered in 1 minute and 34 seconds and therefore the impact on PK is expected to be minimal.

4.2. Deviations

All deviations that occurred during the study phase have been authorized/acknowledged by the Study Director and Individual Scientist, assessed for impact, and documented in the study

Appendix 5

records. All study plan deviations and any SOP deviations that could have impacted the quality or integrity of the study are listed below. None of the deviations were considered to have impacted the overall integrity of this study phase or the interpretation of the study phase results and conclusions.

- Concentrations below the lower limit of quantification (BLQ values) were extrapolated during bioanalysis and these extrapolated values were used in PK evaluation, instead of setting these values to zero.
Since extrapolated was considered reliable, the impact on the study integrity is considered minimal.

4.3. Noncompartmental Analysis

A noncompartmental analysis was used for parameter estimation using Phoenix pharmacokinetic software (version 8.3). For BDT272 in plasma the IV bolus (Period 1) and extravascular (Period 2) model were used for parameter estimation. All parameters were generated from BDT272 individual concentrations in plasma following IV or PO dosing. Parameters were estimated using nominal dose levels and nominal sampling times relative to the start of dose administration (IV dosing) or dose administration (oral dosing). The concentration at time 0 in Period 1 was back extrapolated based on the first 2 observed plasma concentrations and assumed to be 0 in Period 2 for the purpose of parameter estimation. If the second observed concentration in sequence was equal to the first, the concentration at the first observed time point was assigned to time 0. Concentration values reported as below the limit of quantitation (< 20.0 ng/mL) were extrapolated.

The area under the concentration vs. time curve (AUC) was calculated using the linear trapezoidal method with linear interpolation for all profiles with at least 3 consecutive quantifiable concentrations.

When practical, the terminal elimination phase of each concentration versus time curve was identified using at least the final 3 observed concentration values. The slope of the terminal elimination phase was determined using log linear regression on the unweighted concentration data. Parameters relying on the determination of the terminal elimination phase were reported based on the following criterium: adjusted RSQ was > 0.9 . AUC_{0-inf} and dose normalized AUC_{0-inf} were reported irrespective of the $AUC\%extrap$. However, when the $\% extrap$ was $> 25\%$, AUC_{0-inf} and dose normalized AUC_{0-inf} were reported for informational purposes only and should be viewed with caution.

The reported PK parameters are described in the [List of Parameter Abbreviations and Definitions](#). Additional parameters automatically generated by Phoenix, but not required by the Study Plan are maintained in the raw data and are not reported.

4.4. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (sample size [N], arithmetic mean, median [minimum (min) – maximum (max)], standard deviation [SD] and coefficient of variation expressed as a percent [%CV]) and ratios (absolute oral bioavailability) for appropriate grouping and sorting variables were generated. The bioanalytical data, PK parameters, tabulated ratios and descriptive statistics were reported to 3 significant figures, except the individual t_{max} and t_{last} values that were reported to generally align with the PK sampling times presented in the concentration tables,

Appendix 5

as well as the N which was reported with no decimal. Mean and median values reported for observed parameters may not be reflective of the collection time points evaluated on study.

Descriptive statistics for Cl/F and V_z/F were calculated manually with Microsoft Excel using rounded values.

4.5. Computerized Systems

Critical computerized systems used in the study phase are listed below in [Text Table 2](#). All computerized systems used in the conduct of this study have been validated; when a particular system has not satisfied all requirements, appropriate administrative and procedural controls were implemented to assure the quality and integrity of data.

Text Table 2
Computerized Systems

System Name	Description of Data Collected and/or Analyzed
Integral	PK data repository (component of PK analysis platform)
M-Files®	Reporting and collection of 21 CFR Part 11 compliant signature
Phoenix	Computational engine of noncompartmental analysis (component of PK analysis platform)
PK Assist	Phoenix interface for data transfer, data handling and manipulation descriptive statistics and ratios, as well as graphical and tabular output (component of PK analysis platform)

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS**5.1. Pharmacokinetic Evaluation**

([Table 1](#) to [Table 4](#) and [Figure 1](#) to [Figure 5](#))

BDT272 was quantifiable in female Göttingen minipigs up to 2 hours after IV administration. Following PO administration, BDT272 was quantifiable in plasma up to 3, 6, 4 or 4 hours (Animal No. 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively). In both periods, reliable extrapolated values below the limit of quantification were present throughout the 24 hours sampling period. The plasma concentrations of BDT272 increased moderately fast, as median t_{max} values for BDT272 were observed at 3 hours postdose following PO administration and individual t_{max} values ranged from 2 to 3 hours. C_0 could not be back extrapolated in Animal No. 1 and was therefore excluded from descriptive statistics.

Individual $t_{1/2}$ values ranged from 3.81 to 5.88 hours after IV dosing and from 7.90 to 13.1 hours after PO dosing. Average Cl was 1570 mL/hr/kg following IV administration, indicating that BDT272 is a moderately cleared compound. Average V_z was 11000 mL/kg following IV dosing, indicating that BDT272 is highly distributed.

Average absolute oral bioavailability of BDT272 in female Göttingen minipig plasma was low since F was 34.5% based on AUC_{0-inf} and 29.0% based on AUC_{last} .

6. CONCLUSION

BDT272 was administered to four female Göttingen minipigs via single dose intravenous (IV) and oral (PO) administration at dose levels of 0.5 mg/kg (IV) and 2 mg/kg (PO). The pharmacokinetics of BDT272 were evaluated in plasma samples.

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BDT272 was quantifiable in female Göttingen minipigs throughout the 24 hours sampling period following both IV and PO administration. The plasma concentrations of BDT272 increased moderately fast, as median t_{max} values for BDT272 were observed at 3 hours postdose following PO administration.

BDT272 was moderately cleared and highly distributed. Individual $t_{1/2}$ ranged from 3.81 to 5.88 hours after IV dosing and from 7.90 to 13.1 hours after PO dosing. Average absolute oral bioavailability of BDT272 in female Göttingen minipig plasma was low since F was 34.5% based on AUC_{0-inf} and 29.0% based on AUC_{tlast} .

Appendix 5**Table 1 Summary (Mean ± SD) Pharmacokinetic Parameters of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous (Period 1) and Oral (Period 2) Administration of BDT272**

Period	Dose (mg/kg)	C _{max} (ng/mL)	C _{max} /Dose (ng/mL/(mg/kg))	C ₀ (ng/mL)	C ₀ /Dose (ng/mL/(mg/kg))	t _{max} ^a (hr)	t _{last} ^a (hr)	AUC _{tlast} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{tlast} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))
1	0.5	NA	NA	204 ±43.7	407 ±86.5	NA	24.0 (24.0 - 24.0)	314 ±25.7	628 ±51.4
2	2	45.7 ±17.5	22.8 ±8.73	NA	NA	3.00 (2.00 - 3.00)	24.0 (24.0 - 24.0)	367 ±75.0	184 ±37.5
NA: Not applicable.									
^a : Median (minimum - maximum).									
^b : F (AUC _{0-inf}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{0-inf} /Dose.									
^c : F (AUC _{tlast}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{tlast} /Dose.									

Appendix 5**Table 1 Summary (Mean \pm SD) Pharmacokinetic Parameters of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous (Period 1) and Oral (Period 2) Administration of BDT272**

Period	Dose (mg/kg)	t _{1/2} (hr)	AUC _{0-inf} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))	Cl (mL/hr/kg)	Cl/F (mL/hr/kg)	V _z (mL/kg)	V _z /F (mL/kg)	F ^b (%)	F ^c (%)
1	0.5	4.87 \pm 0.859	320 \pm 27.9	640 \pm 55.9	1570 \pm 133	NA	11000 \pm 1580	NA	NA	NA
2	2	10.4 \pm 2.28	458 \pm 108	229 \pm 54.2	NA	4560 \pm 829	NA	67900 \pm 16100	34.5 \pm 5.54	29.0 \pm 3.65
NA: Not applicable.										
^a : Median (minimum - maximum).										
^b : F (AUC _{0-inf}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{0-inf} /Dose.										
^c : F (AUC _{tlast}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{tlast} /Dose.										

Appendix 5**Table 2 Individual Pharmacokinetic Parameters and Summary Statistics of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous Administration of BDT272**

Dose (mg/kg)	Subject	C ₀ (ng/mL)	C ₀ /Dose (ng/mL/(mg/kg))	t _{last} (hr)	AUC _{tlast} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{tlast} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))	t _{1/2} (hr)	AUC _{0-inf} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))	Cl (mL/hr/kg)	V _z (mL/kg)
0.5	1 ^a	150 ^b	300 ^b	24	304	608	5.07	312	623	1600	11700
	2	254	507	24	318	635	3.81	320	639	1560	8590
	3	181	363	24	287	574	4.72	291	583	1720	11700
	4	176	352	24	348	695	5.88	358	716	1400	11800
	N	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
	Mean	204	407	24.0	314	628	4.87	320	640	1570	11000
	SD	43.7	86.5	0.00	25.7	51.4	0.85 9	27.9	55.9	133	1580
	CV%	21.4	21.2	0.00	8.19	8.19	17.6	8.73	8.73	8.45	14.4
	Min	176	352	24.0	287	574	3.81	291	583	1400	8590
	Median	181	363	24.0	311	621	4.89	316	631	1580	11700
	Max	254	507	24.0	348	695	5.88	358	716	1720	11800

^a: Dosing was briefly interrupted; total dose was administered in 1 minute and 34 seconds.
^b: Back-extrapolation was not possible for Animal No. 1 and therefore these values were excluded from descriptive statistics.

Appendix 5

Table 2 Individual Pharmacokinetic Parameters and Summary Statistics of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Oral Administration of BDT272

Dose (mg/kg)	Subject	C _{max} (ng/mL)	C _{max} /Dose (ng/mL/(mg/kg))	t _{max} (hr)	t _{last} (hr)	AUC _{tlast} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{tlast} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))	t _{1/2} (hr)	AUC _{0-inf} (hr*ng/mL)	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (hr*ng/mL/(mg/kg))	Cl/F (mL/hr/kg)	V _z /F (mL/kg)	F ^b (%)	F ^c (%)
2	1	28.8	14.4	3	24	305	153	9.31	365	182	5480	73600	29.3	25.1
	2	54.7	27.4	3	24	383	192	7.90	433	216	4620	52700	33.8	30.2
	3	33.5	16.8	3	24	314	157	13.1	429 ^a	215 ^a	4660 ^a	87900 ^a	36.8 ^a	27.4
	4	65.7	32.9	2	24	467	233	11.4	577	289	3470	57200	40.3	33.6
	N	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	3	3	4
	Mean	45.7	22.8	2.75	24.0	367	184	10.4	458	229	4520	61200	34.5	29.0
	SD	17.5	8.73	0.500	0.00	75.0	37.5	2.28	108	54.2	823	8980	5.54	3.65
	CV%	38.2	38.2	18.2	0.00	20.4	20.4	21.9	23.7	23.7	18.2	14.7	16.1	12.6
	Min	28.8	14.4	2.00	24.0	305	153	7.90	365	182	3470	52700	29.3	25.1
	Median	44.1	22.1	3.00	24.0	348	174	10.4	433	216	4620	57200	33.8	28.8
	Max	65.7	32.9	3.00	24.0	467	233	13.1	577	289	5480	73600	40.3	33.6
^a : Calculated with insufficient plasma concentration data, reported for informational purposes only and excluded from statistics.														
^b : F (AUC _{0-inf}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{0-inf} /Dose.														
^c : F (AUC _{tlast}) = Oral bioavailability calculated with AUC _{tlast} /Dose.														

Appendix 5

Table 3 Summary Concentrations of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous and Oral Administration of BDT272

				Time (hr)									
				0.083	0.25	0.5	1	2	3	4	6	8	24
Dose (mg/kg)	Period	Route		Concentration (ng/mL)									
0.5	1	IV	N	4	4	4	4	4	NA	4	NA	4	4
			Mean	170	138	102	66.0	37.5	NA	17.0	NA	5.41	0.903
			SD	21.3	10.7	16.1	9.28	7.40	NA	1.36	NA	0.251	0.448
			%CV	12.6	7.75	15.8	14.1	19.7	NA	8.01	NA	4.64	49.6
2	2	Oral	N	NA	NA	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
			Mean	NA	NA	9.58	24.9	37.6	40.7	27.8	18.8	15.9	5.40
			SD	NA	NA	8.13	11.9	19.8	11.7	9.02	3.34	2.17	1.18
			%CV	NA	NA	84.9	47.7	52.7	28.9	32.4	17.8	13.7	21.8

NA: Not applicable.

Appendix 5

Table 4 Individual and Summary Concentrations of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous and Oral Administration of BDT272

					Time (hr)									
					0.083	0.25	0.5	1	2	3	4	6	8	24
Dose (mg/kg)	Sex	Period	Route	Subject	Concentration (ng/mL)									
0.5	Female	1	IV	1	150	150	106	57.7	29.1	-	18.4 ^a	-	5.59 ^a	1.23 ^a
				2	200	124	90.4	69.0	41.8	-	16.7 ^a	-	5.46 ^a	0.384 ^a
				3	166	139	88.3	59.4	33.7	-	15.2 ^a	-	5.04 ^a	0.678 ^a
				4	163	140	123	77.7	45.3	-	17.5 ^a	-	5.54 ^a	1.32 ^a
				N	4	4	4	4	4	NA	4	NA	4	4
				Mean	170	138	102	66.0	37.5	NA	17.0	NA	5.41	0.903
				SD	21.3	10.7	16.1	9.28	7.40	NA	1.36	NA	0.251	0.448
				%CV	12.6	7.75	15.8	14.1	19.7	NA	8.01	NA	4.64	49.6
2	Female	2	Oral	1	-	-	6.17 ^a	14.9 ^a	20.8	28.8	19.3 ^a	15.8 ^a	16.2 ^a	4.38 ^a
				2	-	-	4.28 ^a	20.7	36.2	54.7	34.1	23.4	15.7 ^a	4.40 ^a
				3	-	-	6.15 ^a	21.9	27.5	33.5	20.9	17.0 ^a	13.2 ^a	6.16 ^a
				4	-	-	21.7	42.1	65.7	45.6	37.0	19.0 ^a	18.5 ^a	6.64 ^a
				N	NA	NA	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
				Mean	NA	NA	9.58	24.9	37.6	40.7	27.8	18.8	15.9	5.40
				SD	NA	NA	8.13	11.9	19.8	11.7	9.02	3.34	2.17	1.18
				%CV	NA	NA	84.9	47.7	52.7	28.9	32.4	17.8	13.7	21.8
NA: Not applicable.														
^a : BLQ, extrapolated value.														

Appendix 5

Figure 1 Pharmacokinetic Parameter vs. Dose Curves of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous (Period 1) and Oral (Period 2) Administration of BDT272

AUC_{0-∞} (Linear:Linear)

AUC_{0-INF} (Linear:Linear)

Appendix 5

Figure 2 Dose Normalized Pharmacokinetic Parameter vs. Dose Curves of BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous (Period 1) and Oral (Period 2) Administration of BDT272

AUC_{last}/Dose (Linear:Linear)

AUC_{0-inf}/Dose (Linear:Linear)

Appendix 5

Figure 3 Mean (\pm SD) Concentration vs. Time Curves for BDT272 in Female Göttingen Minipig Plasma Following Intravenous (Period 1) and Oral (Period 2) Administration of BDT272

(Log:Linear)

Appendix 5

Figure 4 **BDT272 Plasma Concentration-Time Profiles Following Intravenous Administration of 0.5 mg/kg BDT272 to Female Göttingen Minipigs**

Period 1 (Log:Linear)

Appendix 5

Figure 5 **BDT272 Plasma Concentration-Time Profiles Following Oral Administration of 2 mg/kg BDT272 to Female Göttingen Minipigs**

Period 2 (Log:Linear)

Appendix 5

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